

Synergistic effects of organophosphorus compounds on the extraction of copper from aqueous nitrate medium with *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide into toluene

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Abstract : The extraction behaviour of Cu^{II} from an aqueous nitrate medium employing *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide (HL) in toluene has been investigated in presence of several organophosphorus donors like, tri-octyl phosphine oxide (TOPO), tri-butyl phosphine oxide (TBPO) and tri-phenyl phosphine oxide (TPPO) at pH 5.0. The synergism was found in presence of neutral donors due to the formation of the adduct $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{S})]$ in toluene (S denotes neutral donor). The overall equilibrium constant for each of the three ternary complexes and also for binary system were calculated from extraction data. It is found that the extent of extraction of Cu^{II} in organic phase both as the binary complex as well as ternary complex increase with increase in temperature. The temperature dependence of the equilibrium constants were investigated in order to evaluate the thermodynamic parameters like enthalpy (ΔH°), entropy (ΔS°) and free energy (ΔG°). Extraction mechanism was supported by IR spectra of ternary adduct.

Keywords : Copper(II) extraction, synergistic effect, organophosphorus donors, *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide, AAS study.

Introduction

The separation and recovery of copper(II) from aqueous solutions are very important for both environment protection and resource reuse in hydrometallurgy as the metal acts as trace nutrients both plants and animals^{1,2}. However excessive amounts of copper are toxic to both plants and animals. The selective extraction of copper with different chelating agents from aqueous nitrate medium is a well known technique and has been published in literature³⁻⁷. All those reported works are mainly based on the separation of the metal from different cations with the aid of chelating agents like β -diketones and substituted oximes. However the described extractions are not quantitative and no attempts to enhance the results by the addition of any donor have been reported.

In synergistic extractions, on the other hand, cooperation of the two extractant molecules takes place during the course transfer of the metal ion from aqueous medium into organic phase. One ligand neutralizes the charge of the metal ion while the vacant co-ordination sites or the occupied water molecules are replaced by donor molecule. Overall outcome of such process is the enhancement of extraction of the metal as a consequence of in-

crease in hydrophobicity and the extent of extraction is more than the sum of the values obtained with each extractant independently. Many authors have reported the extraction of divalent metal ions with the mixture of neutral organophosphorus reagents as solvating agents and chelating ligands as complexing agents⁸⁻¹⁴. But the data on synergistic extraction of copper by different combinations of extractant and donor are limited¹⁵⁻²¹. In such cases effects of neutral donors on the extractions of Cu^{II} and allied cations by different types of β -diketones or crown ether have been described. Major aims of such investigations are to separate Cu^{II} from allied cations and its subsequent determinations. However attempts to elucidate the extraction mechanism in terms of thermodynamic parameters have been ignored.

The present investigation deals with the synergistic extraction of copper from aqueous nitrate medium with mixtures of a newly synthesized chelating agent *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide and neutral organophosphorus donor in toluene solvent. The effects of aqueous acidity, extractant concentration, and temperature on the extraction behavior were examined. On the basis of experimental results, composition of extracted adduct and mechanism of

extraction were elucidated. Such conclusion was further confirmed by IR data.

Results and discussion

Effect of equilibration time :

The extraction of Cu^{II} by *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide (HL) in toluene show that the two phase reaction is fairly rapid and the equilibrium is reached within 30 min. The increase of the time of equilibration does not affect the extraction equilibrium.

Effects of organic diluent :

Some organic diluents like CCl_4 , CHCl_3 , *o*-xylene, *p*-xylene, toluene, diethylether, *n*-butanol etc. were chosen to study the effect of diluents upon the extraction of Cu^{II} from aqueous solution of pH 5.0 by *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide. It has been observed that at a fixed concentration of ligand, extraction into toluene is maximum. The trend is as follows : diethylether < *n*-butanol < CHCl_3 < CCl_4 < *o*-xylene < *p*-xylene < toluene (Table 1).

Table 1. The extraction of Cu^{II} with $0.015 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide in different diluent at pH 5

Diluents	<i>D</i>	% <i>E</i>
Toluene	0.784	43.95
<i>p</i> -Xylene	0.652	39.45
<i>o</i> -Xylene	0.565	35.24
Carbontetrachloride	0.398	28.65
Chloroform	0.344	25.59
<i>n</i> -Butanol	0.289	22.45
Diethylether	0.276	21.63

Effect of pH :

Experiments were carried out in different pH of aqueous solution containing Cu^{II} , with fixed concentration of *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide into toluene. In order to establish the optimum pH, the extraction was performed in the pH range of 2–7. The maximum extraction of copper was obtained in the pH range of 4.5–5.5. Hence pH 5 was chosen for further studies (Table 2).

Effect of extractant concentration :

The influence of variation in the *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide concentration on the extraction behavior of copper ions was examined by changing ligand concentration (Table 3) and keeping the metal and acid concentra-

Table 2. The extraction of Cu^{II} with $0.019 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide at different pH

Ligand	pH	<i>D</i>	% <i>E</i>
<i>N</i> -(Thioacetyl)-benzamide	3.5	0.0035	0.348
	4.0	0.036	3.47
	4.3	0.103	9.34
	4.5	0.189	15.89
	4.8	1.15	53.48
	5.0	1.34	57.26
	5.3	1.31	56.71
	5.5	1.47	59.51
	5.8	1.46	59.35
6.0	1.34	57.26	
6.5	1.132	53.09	
7.0	1.054	51.32	

Table 3. Extraction of Cu^{II} with *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide ligand only in toluene at pH 5.0

Ligand	Concentration (mol dm^{-3})	Distribution coefficient (<i>D</i>)	% Extraction
<i>N</i> -(Thioacetyl)-benzamide	0.0037	0.103	9.34
	0.0074	0.187	15.75
	0.011	0.429	30.03
	0.015	0.784	43.95
	0.019	1.365	57.72

tions fixed. With increasing extractant concentration, an increase in the extraction copper was observed. A linear increase of distribution coefficient (*D*) is found with increasing extractant concentration. The log-log plots (Fig. 1) give slope close to 2, indicating the involvement of two molecules of the extractant in the complex formation with copper(II) with subsequent release of two H^+ ions.

$$D = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]_{\text{org}}}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{aq}}} \quad (2)$$

$$\log k = \log D - 2 \log [\text{HL}] - 2\text{pH} \quad (3)$$

Effect of donor concentration on the extraction of copper with N-(thioacetyl)benzamide :

Extraction of Cu^{II} into toluene in presence of pure donors e.g. TOPO, TBPO and TPPO were investigated. Extent of extractions were not very appreciable although presence of such basic donor enhanced the extraction of Cu^{II} by *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide. The effect of neutral

Fig. 1. The variation of distribution coefficient of Cu^{II} with the ligand concentration in presence and absence of neutral donor in toluene at pH 5.0. B : absence of donor, E : presence 0.0029 mol dm⁻³ of TOPO, C : presence 0.0024 mol dm⁻³ of TBPO, D : presence 0.0022 mol dm⁻³ of TPPO.

donor (S) concentration on extraction of Cu^{II} with present ligand (L) at aqueous pH 5 was examined. It was found that the *D* value increases with increasing donor concentration, at fixed ligand concentration. This increased *D* value can be interpreted by assuming the formation of adduct complex CuL₂(S) with neutral organophosphorus donor. This tendency is presumably due to the high hydrophobicity of the extracted complexes CuL₂(S) than CuL₂. The log-log plots (Figs. 1 and 2) of *D_m* against [HL]_{org} and [S]_{org} separately exhibit a linear behavior and the calculated slopes are close to 2, and 1 respectively. This can be accounted by the fact that two molecules of HL and one molecule of donor are present in the extracted adduct. Thus, from the above results, we assume that the stoichiometry of the extracted complex is CuL₂S and the synergic liquid-liquid extraction process of copper(II) can be described by the following equilibrium reaction.

$$K = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{S})]_{\text{org}} [\text{H}^+]^2_{\text{aq}}}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{aq}} \cdot [\text{HL}]^2_{\text{org}} \cdot [\text{S}]} \quad (5)$$

$$D_m = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{S})]_{\text{org}} + [\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]_{\text{org}} + [\text{Cu}(\text{S})]_{\text{org}}}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{aq}}} \quad (6)$$

$$\log K = \log (D_m - D_o - D_S) - 2\log [\text{HL}]_{\text{org}} - \log [\text{S}]_{\text{org}} - 2\text{pH} \quad (7)$$

where, *D_o* is the distribution coefficient of Cu^{II} with *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide only, *D_S* is the distribution coefficient of Cu^{II} with organophosphorus donor only and *D_m* is the distribution coefficient of Cu^{II} with *N*-(thioacetyl)-benzamide in presence of organophosphorus donor.

The adduct formation reaction in the organic phase may be represented as

And accordingly,

$$\log K_S = \log K - \log k \quad (9)$$

Degree of synergism in extraction :

The extraction of copper(II) with pure neutral organophosphorus extractants (*D_S*) as mentioned before were negligible under the present experimental conditions. However, with mixtures of *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide and neutral organophosphorus extractants, a considerable synergistic enhancement in the extraction of copper(II) was observed. Enhancement of extraction of copper(II) in presence of neutral donor, possibly due to replacement of water molecules of inner coordination sphere of metal by basic donors may be described as synergistic effect.

Fig. 2. The variation of distribution coefficient of Cu^{II} with neutral donor in presence of fixed ligand concentration in toluene at pH 5.0. [Ligand] = 0.0074 mol dm⁻³, A : TOPO B : TBPO, C : TPPO.

The degree of synergism is quantified by synergistic coefficient (S.C.),

where,

$$S.C. = \log [D_m / (D_o + D_s)] \quad (10)$$

The apparent stability constant (β) of metal-ligand-donor adduct is given by :

$$\beta = (D_m - D_o) / D_o [\text{donor}] \quad (11)$$

Synergism was observed at all the compositions studied. Keeping the concentration of ligand (0.0074 mol dm⁻³) constant it was observed that the synergistic coefficient increased with an increase in the concentration of the

synergist (Table 4), at fixed pH of the aqueous phase. Similarly, keeping organophosphorus donor concentration constant, the synergistic coefficient increased with an increase in the ligand concentration in the organic phase at a given acid concentration (Table 5). Again the trend in S.C. and β -value shown in Table 4 for the organophosphorus donors taken up here follow the order : TOPO > TBPO > TPPO. This trend can be correlated with the relative basic natures of the donors. Somewhat similar trend was seen in the synergistic extraction of other transition metals and actinides²²⁻²⁴.

Table 4. Synergistic extraction of Cu^{II} by mixture of chelating ligand and organophosphorus donor
Fixed concentration of ligand = 0.0074 mol dm⁻³, pH = 5.0, solvent = toluene, D₀ = 0.187

Donor	Concn. of donor (mol dm ⁻³)	D _{mix}	ΔD	% Extraction	S.C.	$\beta \times 10^2$ (mol ⁻¹)
TOPO	0.0029	0.396	0.209	28.36	0.325	3.85
	0.0043	0.519	0.332	34.17	0.443	4.13
	0.0059	0.617	0.43	38.16	0.518	3.89
	0.0071	0.769	0.582	43.47	0.614	4.38
	0.0089	0.987	0.801	49.67	0.723	4.80
TBPO	0.0024	0.312	0.125	23.78	0.223	2.78
	0.0033	0.391	0.204	28.12	0.321	3.30
	0.0047	0.456	0.269	31.32	0.387	3.16
	0.0057	0.547	0.366	35.32	0.467	3.37
	0.0069	0.672	0.485	40.19	0.556	3.75
TPPO	0.0022	0.240	0.054	19.35	0.109	1.28
	0.0031	0.358	0.171	26.35	0.283	2.94
	0.0043	0.465	0.278	31.74	0.395	3.34
	0.0059	0.605	0.418	37.69	0.509	3.78
	0.0064	0.645	0.458	38.68	0.538	3.82

S.C. = Synergistic coefficient = $\log D_{mix} / (D_o)$

$\beta = (D_{mix} - D_o) / D_o$ [donor], apparent constant.

Table 5. Synergistic extraction of Cu^{II} by mixture of chelating ligand and organophosphorus extractant at a fixed concentration of donor
with different concentration of ligand
pH = 5.0, solvent = toluene, [TOPO] = 0.0029 mol dm⁻³, [TBPO] = 0.0024 mol dm⁻³, [TPPO] = 0.0022 mol dm⁻³

Donor	Concn. of ligand (mol dm ⁻³)	D ₀	D _m	ΔD	% Extraction	S.C.	$\beta \times 10^2$ (mol ⁻¹)
TOPO	0.0074	0.187	0.456	0.269	31.31	0.387	4.97
	0.0110	0.429	0.972	0.543	49.29	0.356	4.37
	0.0149	0.784	1.850	1.061	64.92	0.373	4.66
TBPO	0.0074	0.187	0.396	0.209	28.36	0.326	4.66
	0.0110	0.429	0.967	0.538	49.16	0.353	5.23
	0.0149	0.784	1.790	1.006	63.63	0.358	5.35
TPPO	0.0074	0.187	0.312	0.1250	23.78	0.223	3.04
	0.0110	0.429	0.896	0.467	47.25	0.319	4.95
	0.0149	0.784	1.650	0.886	62.27	0.324	5.14

Effect of temperature :

Temperature effect on the extraction of copper(II) ions by the ligand and mixture of ligand and organophosphorus donors have been studied also. The results are illustrated in Fig. 3. In the case of binary and ternary extraction system, the higher temperature leads to increase in the copper extraction at this aqueous acidity. The equilibrium extraction constants $\log k$ and $\log K$ for the studied complexes were calculated from the equilibrium metal

Fig. 3. Temperature variation of equilibrium constant of ternary extraction system in toluene.

concentration in the organic and aqueous phase using eqs. (3) and (7). From the values of equilibrium extraction constant at the temperature range investigated, the Vant's Hoff equation²⁵ was used to calculate the enthalpy change.

$$\log K = -\Delta H/2.303RT + \Delta S/2.303RT$$

The plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$ is a straight line where the slope gives the enthalpy of reaction (ΔH°) and intercept corresponds to entropy (ΔS°) value. The values of $\log K$ as well as ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° are shown in Table 6.

The positive values of ΔH° show the endothermic nature of all the three systems under investigation i.e. all of

Table 6. Equilibrium constants for binary and ternary system

Binary system	Ternary system				
	Ligand	$\log k$	Donor	$\log K$	$\log K_S$
<i>N</i> -(Thioacetyl)-benzamide		-6.89	TOPO	1.68	8.57
			TBPO	1.32	8.21
			TPPO	1.27	8.16

the three ternary extractions are enthalpy disfavoured, may be due to replacement of water molecules by donors. Similar behavior was reported by many authors for copper extraction^{26,27}. On the other hand the positive entropy changes (ΔS°) imply that copper cations are being transferred from the highly ordered water structure to the disordered structure in organic phase²⁸. Actually extensive disruption of hydration sphere takes place in course of formation of adduct causing increase in entropy. Overall free-energy changes in all the three metal-ligand-adduct systems are negative indicating the spontaneity of ternary extractions. Again, TOPO-adduct system corresponds to maximum value of ΔG° , which is attributed to its strongest basic character in compare to other two phosphine oxides. Hence the thermodynamic data leads to the conclusion that the synergistic effect is manifested by replacement of water molecules from inner sphere of metal by organophosphorous donors, making the adduct more hydrophobic.

Infra-red spectroscopy :

The infra-red spectrum of the extracted compound was recorded in organic solution, by evaporating toluene solvent. The infra-red spectrum shows that the $\nu_{C=S}$ band frequency and $\nu_{C=O}$ band frequency has shifted to the little down field from the free ligand. The $\nu_{C=O}$ band had shifted from 1684 cm^{-1} in free ligand to 1685 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{C=S}$ band shifted from 1175 cm^{-1} in free ligand to 1149 cm^{-1} ²⁹ in the extracted complex. Similarly the $\nu_{P=O}$ band has been shifted from 1144 cm^{-1} in free phosphine

Table 7. Thermodynamic parameters related to binary and ternary extraction system

Species	ΔH°	ΔS°	ΔG°
	(kJ mol ⁻¹)	(JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	(kJ mol ⁻¹) at 27 °C
Ligand	62.25 ± 0.21	73.97 ± 0.23	40.06 ± 0.11
Cu ^{II} -ligand-TOPO	38.56 ± 0.12	164.21 ± 0.35	-10.59 ± 0.24
Cu ^{II} -ligand-TBPO	81.61 ± 0.34	303.35 ± 0.14	-9.08 ± 0.22
Cu ^{II} -ligand-TPPO	79.88 ± 0.25	252.44 ± 0.22	-8.05 ± 0.11

oxide donor to 1110 cm^{-1} which characterize the P-O-Cu bond in adduct complex. All these data clearly support the formation of the adduct complex is $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{S})]$ in the organic phase.

Experimental

Reagent and instruments :

The chelating ligand *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide was synthesised in our laboratory by the reaction of benzoyl chloride derived from benzoic acid and thioacetamide, obtained from Aldrich, USA. The donor reagents used in this work e.g. tri-octyl phosphine oxide phosphate (TOPO), tri-butyl phosphine oxide (TBPO), tri-phenyl phosphine oxide (TPPO), were also procured from Aldrich, USA. The solvents used in the present work were purified by standard procedures. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. A stock solution of copper was prepared by dissolving $\sim 1.00\text{ g}$ A.R. $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, in deionised water and working stock containing 100 ppm Cu^{II} was prepared by appropriate dilution. A Varian model spectra 55B flame atomic absorption spectrometer was used for measuring the concentration of Cu^{II} in an air-acetylene flame. A copper hollow cathode lamp, was used as light source operated at 10 mA . The wavelength was set at 324.7 nm resonance line and the spectral band pass at 0.5 nm . A time-constant of 0.2 s was used for peak height evaluation. The air flow rate was set at 3.5 L min^{-1} and acetylene flow rate at 1.5 L min^{-1} . Microanalysis of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content of the synthetic ligand were achieved in a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS-O elemental analyzer. Infrared spectra of ligands and adduct complexes were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. A Systronics model 335 digital pH-meter equipped with a single electrode was used for pH measurement. For the study of the temperature effect, equilibrations were carried out in a temperature controlled mechanical shaker.

Synthesis and characterisation of the chelating agent :

The chelating ligand was synthesized by the general condensation reaction between benzoyl chloride and thioacetamide (1 : 1). The starting material, A.R. benzoic acid (2.00 g) was refluxed for 2 h with successive addition of thionyl chloride. The excess of chlorinating agent was removed by slow evaporation. In a beaker, a saturated solution of thioacetamide (1.24 g) in double distilled nitrobenzene solvent, free from any water, was prepared. The solvent was purified by drying over calcium oxide followed by distillation before use. This thioacetamide solution was then condensed with benzoyl chloride for 1 h over a boiling water bath. The brown color precipitate so appeared was separated by filtration process, recrystallized from chloroform solvent and dried. The dried compound melts at $(94 \pm 2^\circ)$. The proposed formula of the ligand (Fig. 4) is in good agreement with the stoichiometries obtained from their CHN elemental analysis data as well as IR and $^1\text{H NMR}$ data. From CHN analysis, Found : C, 60.26; H, 4.98, N, 7.65. Calcd. C, 60.33; H, 5.02; N, 7.82%. In the IR spectrum of the ligand, absence of band at 3760 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} (present in original acid) and presence of sharp peaks at 1689 cm^{-1} ³⁰ corresponding to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ support that only hydroxyl group of acid take part in condensation reaction. Further observation of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ at 1175 cm^{-1} established that the thio group in thioacetamide is not affected in the course of synthesis. NMR data also agrees well at $\delta 7.6\text{ ppm}$ (5H, aromatic), methyl proton occur at $\delta 2.3\text{ ppm}$ (3H, s, methyl group), amide proton -HN- arise at $\delta 8.1\text{ ppm}$ (1H, s, proton)³¹.

Extraction procedure :

In the general extraction procedure, 5 mL aqueous solution containing $100\text{ }\mu\text{g}$ of Cu^{II} solution was adjusted to a pH 5.00 and extracted with equal volume of toluene solution of different concentrations of chelating ligand for a period of 30 min in a mechanical shaker. Ionic

Fig. 4. Synthesis of chelating ligand *N*-(thioacetyl)benzamide.

strength of the solution was kept fixed at 0.5 mol dm^{-3} by using KNO_3 reagent. For synergistic study, organic phase was mixed with appropriate donor reagent of desired concentration. After the equilibration, two phases were separated and the Cu^{II} content in aqueous phase was analysed for its absorbance by AAS. The distribution coefficient of metal ion was calculated from the Cu^{II} concentrations in the aqueous phase before and after attaining equilibrium from the following equation :

$$D = C_{\text{M (org)}}/C_{\text{M (aq)}} = (C_{\text{MO}} - C_{\text{M}})/C_{\text{M}}$$

where C_{MO} and C_{M} denote analytical Cu^{II} concentrations in the aqueous phase before and after attaining partition equilibrium, respectively.

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